

My Investigation of the Zeta Function and the Riemann Hypothesis

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Abstract:

Bernhard Riemann is well known as (and widely accepted to be) the pioneer of Complex Analysis. He is most particularly famous for his 1859 paper and the hypothesis that followed thereafter (for some 166 years). His paper implied that each and every complex root of the Zeta function has a real part of “0.5”.

Many Mathematicians after his time were deeply fascinated by the problem and attempted to prove it in their own ways. But, due to the passage of decades and decades of time (without any proof in sight), this problem became important enough to be included in the list of 23 notable unsolved problems of the century by David Hilbert (and later, by the Clay Math Institute).

As I got fascinated by this problem as well, I started investigating this problem from a fresh perspective. This paper reflects an overall account of my year-long investigation of the Zeta function, and it contains my proof of the Riemann Hypothesis as well (a proof which I believe is correct).

My Account:

My Investigation of the Zeta Function began with the Analytic Continuation function of the Zeta Function Riemann proposed roughly 166 years ago (Riemann, 1859). A modified version of the reflection function is written below (Titchmarsh and Heath-Brown, 1986).

$$\zeta(s) = \frac{(2\pi)^s}{\pi} \sin\left(\frac{\pi s}{2}\right) \Gamma(1-s)\zeta(1-s)$$

(1)

Initially I played around with this function, trying to find its modulus when $s = x + iy$ (where $i = \sqrt{-1}$). I eventually succeeded by using the De Moivre’s theorem. I was able to find its modulus that way.

Over the course of my investigation, I realized that this is a reflection function in which at least one side has to have a Zeta definition valid within the intervals “ $(1, \infty)$ or $(-\infty, 0)$ ” and “ $(0, 0.5]$ or $[0.5, 1)$ ” (to define the function almost everywhere (except at the boundaries which could be defined by its limits)).

I then encountered the Dirichlet-Eta definition (Titchmarsh and Heath-Brown, 1986) over the course of my research. It happened to be a very simple and wonderful definition of the Zeta function

for me (valid within the entire open interval $x \in (0,1)$). I then took the modulus of that function (via the De Moivre's theorem). The function is as follows.

$$|\zeta(s)| = \frac{\left| \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{n^s} \right|}{|1 - 2^{1-s}|} = \frac{\sqrt{\left[\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n+1} \cos(y \ln(n))}{n^x} \right]^2 + \left[\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n+1} \sin(y \ln(n))}{n^x} \right]^2}}{\sqrt{1 - 2^{2-x} \cos(y \ln(2)) + 2^{2-2x}}} \quad (2)$$

My initial approach was to establish a lower bound for this modulus function within the interval $x \in (0,1)$ (a specific type of 2D lower bound whose derivative with respect to "x" turns to zero when $x = 0.5$ & $z = 0$). My initial candidates were the lower half of a unit circle centered at $(x, z) = (0.5, 0.5)$ and the Riemann-Xi function centered at $x = 0.5$ as well. Based on my initial observations, the unit circle lower bound seemed to fail. But, I intuitively believed that the modified Riemann-Xi function could happen to be a lower bound of the Zeta function when $x \in (0,1)$. Nevertheless, I wasn't able to get anywhere with that approach (I tried to use some inductive methods but I couldn't get anywhere with that approach).

When I was studying some plots of the above modulus function, I noticed that the Zeta function always had a lower bound of either $|\zeta(1 \pm iy)|$ or $|\zeta(0.5 \pm iy)|$ when $x \in (0, 0.5]$ and when $y \geq 14.134725..$ (It seemed to behave this way a little before the y-value as well, upto a point where $|\zeta(x \pm iy)| = 1, x \in \{0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5\}$ seemed to intersect, and form a straight line with respect to the x-axis). It also seemed to have an upper bound of $|\zeta(0 \pm iy)|$ in the same "x" and "y" intervals. I also noticed that all the minima of $|\zeta(1 \pm iy)|$ were located at the points where $y = \frac{2n\pi}{\ln(2)} \forall n \in \mathbb{N}$ as well. These seemed to be some interesting properties of the Zeta function.

I then found the partial derivatives with respect to "x" and "y" of the above modulus function (2) and attempted to use Rolle's theorem to prove the Riemann Hypothesis (which says that the non-trivial zeroes of the Zeta function have a real part of 0.5). But only the partial derivative of that function with respect to "x" seemed relevant. I thus used the partial derivative with respect to "x" to proceed further. But, after a lot of attempts, I realized that the definition led nowhere. I learnt a lot from the Dirichlet-Eta definition though. So that was a positive.

And then one day, I had a thought (during the early morning hours of Krishna Jayanthi in 2025). I was restless and walking back and forth in the Ooty bus stand, listening to Ninurta by Audiomachine. Walking and listening to my playlist mostly consisting of pure music is a habit of mine. I must have easily walked like this for thousands of hours over the past eight years. Pure music speaks a language of its own.

In my thought, I imagined the Zeta function as a ribbon dancer with a pair of infinitely long ribbons tied to her ankles / feet. She danced along the line $x = 0.5$ & $z = 0$ and generated the entire function using her ribbons. Sometimes, she danced quite vibrantly and made some long jumps. Sometimes, she made some short jumps. But she danced vibrantly along this line nonetheless, always landing perfectly on the line " $x = 0.5$ & $z = 0$ "! She was full of energy in my imagination!

This vision made me realize why the points where a function is equal to zero are called "root" points. Like the roots of a tree, the roots of a function are responsible for generating the entire function (along with its poles, which I realized later). This vision ultimately led me to the following Hadamard product definition (Titchmarsh and Heath-Brown, 1986). This infinite product is

absolutely convergent (Davenport and Montgomery, 1980). In the following calculations, $y \geq 0$, $s = x + iy$, $s' = 1 - s$, $\rho_n = a_n + ib_n$, and γ is the Euler-Mascheroni constant.

$$|\zeta(s)|^2 = \frac{\left| \left[e^{\left[\ln(2\pi) - 1 - \frac{\gamma}{2} \right] s} \right] \left[\prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[1 - \left(\frac{s}{\rho_n} \right) \right] \left[e^{\frac{s}{\rho_n}} \right] \right] \right|^2}{\left| 2(s-1)\Gamma\left(1 + \left(\frac{s}{2}\right)\right) \right|^2} = \frac{\left| \left[e^{\left[\ln(2\pi) - 1 - \frac{\gamma}{2} \right] s} \right] \left[\prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[1 - \left(\frac{s}{1-\rho_n} \right) \right] \left[e^{\frac{s}{1-\rho_n}} \right] \right] \right|^2}{\left| 2(s-1)\Gamma\left(1 + \left(\frac{s}{2}\right)\right) \right|^2} \quad (3)$$

$$|\zeta(s)|^2 = \frac{\left[e^{\left[\ln(2\pi) - 1 - \frac{\gamma}{2} \right] 2x} \right] \left[\prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\left(\frac{(a_n - x)^2 + (b_n - y)^2}{a_n^2 + b_n^2} \right) \right] \left[e^{\frac{2(xa_n + yb_n)}{a_n^2 + b_n^2}} \right] \right]}{4[(x-1)^2 + y^2] \left[\int_0^{\infty} (e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \cos\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right)) dt \right]^2 + \left[\int_0^{\infty} (e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \sin\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right)) dt \right]^2 \right]} \quad (4)$$

$$|\zeta(s)|^2 = \frac{\left[e^{\left[\ln(2\pi) - 1 - \frac{\gamma}{2} \right] 2x} \right] \left[\prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\left(\frac{(1 - a_n - x)^2 + (b_n + y)^2}{(1 - a_n)^2 + b_n^2} \right) \right] \left[e^{\frac{2(x(1-a_n) - yb_n)}{(1-a_n)^2 + b_n^2}} \right] \right]}{4[(x-1)^2 + y^2] \left[\int_0^{\infty} (e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \cos\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right)) dt \right]^2 + \left[\int_0^{\infty} (e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \sin\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right)) dt \right]^2 \right]} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \ln(|\zeta(s)|^2) &= 2 \left[\ln(2\pi) - 1 - \frac{\gamma}{2} \right] x + \left[\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [\ln((a_n - x)^2 + (b_n - y)^2)] \right] + 2 \left[\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{(xa_n + yb_n)}{a_n^2 + b_n^2} \right] \right] \\ &\quad - \left[\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [\ln(a_n^2 + b_n^2)] \right] - \ln(4) - \ln[(x-1)^2 + y^2] \\ &\quad - \ln \left[\int_0^{\infty} (e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \cos\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right)) dt \right]^2 + \left[\int_0^{\infty} (e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \sin\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right)) dt \right]^2 \right] \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial}{\partial x} |\zeta(s)|^2 &= f(x, y) \\
&= [|\zeta(x + iy)|^2] \left[2 \left[\ln(2\pi) - 1 - \frac{\gamma}{2} \right] - \left[\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{2(a_n - x)}{[(a_n - x)^2 + (b_n - y)^2]} \right] \right] \right. \\
&\quad + 2 \left[\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{(a_n)}{a_n^2 + b_n^2} \right] \right] - \frac{2(x-1)}{[(x-1)^2 + y^2]} \\
&\quad - \frac{\left[\int_0^{\infty} \left(e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \cos\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right) \right) dt \right] \left[\int_0^{\infty} \left(e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \cos\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right) \ln(t) \right) dt \right]}{\left[\int_0^{\infty} \left(e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \cos\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right) \right) dt \right]^2 + \left[\int_0^{\infty} \left(e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \sin\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right) \right) dt \right]^2} \\
&\quad - \frac{\left[\int_0^{\infty} \left(e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \sin\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right) \right) dt \right] \left[\int_0^{\infty} \left(e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \sin\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right) \ln(t) \right) dt \right]}{\left[\int_0^{\infty} \left(e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \cos\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right) \right) dt \right]^2 + \left[\int_0^{\infty} \left(e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \sin\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right) \right) dt \right]^2} \right]
\end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
|\zeta(s)|^2 &= |\zeta(x + iy)|^2 = \left[\frac{(2\pi)^{2x}}{\pi^2} \right] \left[\sin^2\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) + \sinh^2\left(\frac{\pi y}{2}\right) \right] [|\Gamma(1 - x - iy)|^2] [|\zeta(1 - x - iy)|^2] \\
&= |\zeta(x - iy)|^2 \\
&= \left[\frac{(2\pi)^{2x}}{\pi^2} \right] \left[\sin^2\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) + \sinh^2\left(\frac{\pi y}{2}\right) \right] [|\Gamma(1 - x + iy)|^2] [|\zeta(1 - x + iy)|^2]
\end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial}{\partial x} |\zeta(s)|^2 &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x} |\zeta(x + iy)|^2 \\
&= \left[\frac{e^{\left[\ln(2\pi) - 1 - \frac{\gamma}{2} \right] 2x} \left[\prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\left(\frac{(a_n - x)^2 + (b_n - y)^2}{a_n^2 + b_n^2} \right) \right] \left[e^{\frac{2(x a_n + y b_n)}{a_n^2 + b_n^2}} \right] \right]}{4[(x-1)^2 + y^2] \left[\int_0^{\infty} \left(e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \cos\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right) \right) dt \right]^2 + \left[\int_0^{\infty} \left(e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \sin\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right) \right) dt \right]^2} \right] [2 \ln(2\pi)] \\
&\quad - 1 - \frac{\gamma}{2} - \left[\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{2(a_n - x)}{[(a_n - x)^2 + (b_n - y)^2]} \right] \right] + 2 \left[\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{(a_n)}{a_n^2 + b_n^2} \right] \right] - \frac{2(x-1)}{[(x-1)^2 + y^2]} \\
&\quad - \frac{\left[\int_0^{\infty} \left(e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \cos\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right) \right) dt \right] \left[\int_0^{\infty} \left(e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \cos\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right) \ln(t) \right) dt \right]}{\left[\int_0^{\infty} \left(e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \cos\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right) \right) dt \right]^2 + \left[\int_0^{\infty} \left(e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \sin\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right) \right) dt \right]^2} \\
&\quad - \frac{\left[\int_0^{\infty} \left(e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \sin\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right) \right) dt \right] \left[\int_0^{\infty} \left(e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \sin\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right) \ln(t) \right) dt \right]}{\left[\int_0^{\infty} \left(e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \cos\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right) \right) dt \right]^2 + \left[\int_0^{\infty} \left(e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \sin\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right) \right) dt \right]^2}
\end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

At root points $\rho_n = a_n + ib_n$, we have to take the factor $[(a_n - x)^2 + (b_n - y)^2]$ from the infinite product and multiply it within the second main square bracket of the product, to make it

convergent at root points. This modification should take place before the root point substitution (which goes without saying). Definition 9 is valid when x belongs to $(0, \infty)$.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} |\zeta(s)|^2 = & \left[\frac{(2\pi)^{2x}}{\pi^2} \left[\sin^2\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) + \sinh^2\left(\frac{\pi y}{2}\right) \right] [|\Gamma(1-x-iy)|^2] [|\zeta(1-x-iy)|^2] \right] \left[2 \left[\ln(2\pi) \right. \right. \\ & - 1 - \frac{Y}{2} \left. \left. - \left[\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{2(a_n-x)}{[(a_n-x)^2 + (b_n-y)^2]} \right] \right] + 2 \left[\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{(a_n)}{[a_n^2 + b_n^2]} \right] \right] - \frac{2(x-1)}{[(x-1)^2 + y^2]} \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. \frac{\left[\int_0^{\infty} \left(e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \cos\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right) \right) dt \right] \left[\int_0^{\infty} \left(e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \cos\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right) \ln(t) \right) dt \right]}{\left[\int_0^{\infty} \left(e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \cos\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right) \right) dt \right]^2 + \left[\int_0^{\infty} \left(e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \sin\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right) \right) dt \right]^2} \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. - \frac{\left[\int_0^{\infty} \left(e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \sin\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right) \right) dt \right] \left[\int_0^{\infty} \left(e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \sin\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right) \ln(t) \right) dt \right]}{\left[\int_0^{\infty} \left(e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \cos\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right) \right) dt \right]^2 + \left[\int_0^{\infty} \left(e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \sin\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right) \right) dt \right]^2} \right] \right] \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

At root points, $|\zeta(1-x-iy)|^2 = |\zeta(x+iy)|^2 = 0$ (since none of the other factors of equation 1 can make the Zeta function to be zero in the critical strip). And, from the symmetry of the Zeta function with respect to $y = 0$ (which also means that the derivative at both sides of the symmetry should be the same), $|\zeta(1-x-iy)|^2 = |\zeta(1-x+iy)|^2 = |\zeta(x-iy)|^2 = 0$ (from Equations 1 & 8). Therefore, equation 10 becomes,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} |\zeta(x-iy)|^2 \text{ at root points} & = \left[\frac{(2\pi)^{2x}}{\pi^2} \left[\sin^2\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) + \sinh^2\left(\frac{\pi y}{2}\right) \right] [|\Gamma(1-x-iy)|^2] [|\zeta(x-iy)|^2] \right] \left[2 \left[\ln(2\pi) \right. \right. \\ & - 1 - \frac{Y}{2} \left. \left. - \left[\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{2(a_n-x)}{[(a_n-x)^2 + (b_n+y)^2]} \right] \right] + 2 \left[\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{(a_n)}{[a_n^2 + b_n^2]} \right] \right] - \frac{2(x-1)}{[(x-1)^2 + y^2]} \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. \frac{\left[\int_0^{\infty} \left(e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \cos\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right) \right) dt \right] \left[\int_0^{\infty} \left(e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \cos\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right) \ln(t) \right) dt \right]}{\left[\int_0^{\infty} \left(e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \cos\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right) \right) dt \right]^2 + \left[\int_0^{\infty} \left(e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \sin\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right) \right) dt \right]^2} \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. - \frac{\left[\int_0^{\infty} \left(e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \sin\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right) \right) dt \right] \left[\int_0^{\infty} \left(e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \sin\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right) \ln(t) \right) dt \right]}{\left[\int_0^{\infty} \left(e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \cos\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right) \right) dt \right]^2 + \left[\int_0^{\infty} \left(e^{-t} t^{\frac{x}{2}} \sin\left(\frac{y \ln(t)}{2}\right) \right) dt \right]^2} \right] \right] \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

At root points, the partial derivative of the square of the modulus of the Zeta function with respect to " x " is also zero (i.e. $\frac{\partial}{\partial x} |\zeta(s)|^2 = 0$). Therefore, by equating equations 11 & 7 (which is possible due to the symmetry about the plane $y = 0$ (i.e. The derivative at both sides of the symmetry must be the same, as both sides will have the same curvature)), and simplifying the resulting partial derivative $\frac{\partial}{\partial x} |\zeta(s)|^2$ at root points equation further using the Bernoulli's / L'hôpital's rule (to avoid division by zero. The second derivative of $|\zeta(x+iy)|^2$ with respect to " x " at any and all root points is not equal to zero), we get the condition that is necessary for the non-trivial root

points of the Zeta function to exist (since the following equation has been obtained from the presumption that $|\zeta(x + iy)|^2 = |\zeta(1 - x - iy)|^2 = |\zeta(1 - x + iy)|^2 = |\zeta(x - iy)|^2 = 0$ (which may be possible for root points only inside the critical strip), the following equation is valid only for the non-trivial roots of the Zeta function).

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} |\zeta(s)|^2 \text{ at root points} = \left[\left(\frac{(2\pi)^{2x}}{\pi^2} \right) \left[\sin^2 \left(\frac{\pi x}{2} \right) + \sinh^2 \left(\frac{\pi y}{2} \right) \right] [|\Gamma(1 - x - iy)|^2] \right] f(x, y)$$

$$= f(x, y)$$

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow a_n, y \rightarrow b_n} \frac{f(x, y)}{f(x, y)} = \lim_{x \rightarrow a_n, y \rightarrow b_n} \frac{\frac{\partial f}{\partial x}}{\frac{\partial f}{\partial x}} = 1$$

$$\left(\frac{(2\pi)^{2x}}{\pi^2} \right) \left[\sin^2 \left(\frac{\pi x}{2} \right) + \sinh^2 \left(\frac{\pi y}{2} \right) \right] [|\Gamma(1 - x - iy)|^2] = 1$$

(12)

The LHS of equation 12 (which is our root condition) is a constant with respect to “x” (when “x” belongs to [0, 0.5] for the purposes of this calculation). We can thus infer from condition 12 that the product $\left[\sin^2 \left(\frac{\pi x}{2} \right) + \sinh^2 \left(\frac{\pi y}{2} \right) \right] [|\Gamma(1 - x - iy)|^2]$ must be equal to $\left[\left(\frac{(2\pi)^{2x}}{\pi^2} \right)^{-1} \right]$. It can be easily proved that this is possible only when $x = 0.5$. And we can confirm it visually that it is impossible for the product to be a constant for any other value of “x”. The proof is as follows.

$$|\Gamma(s)||\Gamma(1 - s)| = \frac{\pi}{|\sin(\pi s)|}$$

$$|\Gamma(x + iy)||\Gamma(1 - x - iy)| = \frac{\pi}{|\sin(\pi s)|}$$

$$|\Gamma(0.5 + iy)||\Gamma(0.5 - iy)| = \frac{\pi}{|\sin(\pi(0.5 + iy))|}$$

$$|\Gamma(0.5 - iy)|^2 = \frac{\pi}{\cos(i\pi y)} = \frac{\pi}{\cosh(\pi y)}$$

(13)

$$0.5 + \sinh^2 \left(\frac{\pi y}{2} \right) = 0.5 - \sin^2 \left(\frac{i\pi y}{2} \right) = 0.5 - 0.5 + \frac{\cos(i\pi y)}{2} = \frac{\cosh(\pi y)}{2}$$

(14)

From equations 13 and 14, we can establish that the left-hand side of equation 12 is always equal to 1 when $x = 0.5$. Now the question becomes whether the product (that is not dependent on the y-variable, as the result $\left[\left(\frac{(2\pi)^{2x}}{\pi^2} \right)^{-1} \right]$ is dependent only on the x-variable), can be a constant for any other value of “x”. A picture is worth a thousand words in this instance.

Plot [Gamma(1-x)|sin(pi(x)/2)]^2, [Gamma(1-x-i14)|sin(pi(x+14))]

NATURAL LANGUAGE

MATH INPUT

Input interpretation

$$\left(|\Gamma(1-x)| \left| \sin\left(\pi \times \frac{x}{2}\right) \right| \right)^2$$

plot

$$\left(|\Gamma(1-x-i \times 14)| \left| \sin\left(\pi \left(\frac{1}{2}(x+i \times 14)\right)\right) \right| \right)^2$$

$x = 0$ to 0.5

$$\frac{\pi^2}{(2\pi)^{2x}}$$

Plot

We can thus establish from this plot that it is virtually impossible for the product to be a constant unless $x = 0.5$. The root condition and the plot therefore establish the hypothesis of Riemann without any reasonable doubt in my opinion.

There might be some scepticism about whether the product should become a constant with respect to "x". For argument sake, if it didn't become a constant, then the product should definitely have at least one extremum with respect to "x" (when "x" belongs to (0, 0.5)). Let's check if that's true.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\left[\sin^2 \left(\frac{\pi x}{2} \right) + \sinh^2 \left(\frac{\pi y}{2} \right) \right] [|\Gamma(1-x-iy)|^2] \right] \\
&= \left[\left[\sin^2 \left(\frac{\pi x}{2} \right) + \sinh^2 \left(\frac{\pi y}{2} \right) \right] \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\Gamma(1-x-iy)|^2] \right] \right] \\
&+ \left[\left[\pi \sin \left(\frac{\pi x}{2} \right) \cos \left(\frac{\pi x}{2} \right) \right] [|\Gamma(1-x-iy)|^2] \right]
\end{aligned}$$

(15)

By using the Digamma function,

$$\begin{aligned}
\Psi(s') &= \Psi(1-x-iy) = \left[\frac{d}{ds'} [\ln [\Gamma(1-x-iy)]] \right] \\
&= \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\ln [\Gamma(1-x-iy)]] \left[\frac{\partial x}{\partial s'} \right] \right] + \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial y} [\ln [\Gamma(1-x-iy)]] \left[\frac{\partial y}{\partial s'} \right] \right] \\
&= \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\ln [\Gamma(1-x-iy)]] \left[\frac{1}{\frac{\partial s'}{\partial x}} \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} [\ln [\Gamma(1-x-iy)]] \left[\frac{1}{\frac{\partial s'}{\partial y}} \right] \\
&= \frac{- \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\Gamma(1-x-iy)] \right]}{\Gamma(1-x-iy)} + i \frac{\left[\frac{\partial}{\partial y} [\Gamma(1-x-iy)] \right]}{\Gamma(1-x-iy)}
\end{aligned}$$

and the following relation,

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\Gamma(1-x-iy)|^2] &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[[Re(\Gamma(1-x-iy))]^2 + [Im(\Gamma(1-x-iy))]^2 \right] \\
&= \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\left[Re((\Gamma(1-x-iy))) + iIm((\Gamma(1-x-iy))) \right] \left[Re((\Gamma(1-x-iy))) \right. \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left. - iIm((\Gamma(1-x-iy))) \right] \right] \\
&= [\Gamma(1-x-iy)] \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\Gamma(1-x+iy)] \right] + [\Gamma(1-x+iy)] \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\Gamma(1-x-iy)] \right] \\
&= [|\Gamma(1-x-iy)|^2] \left[\frac{\left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\Gamma(1-x+iy)] \right]}{\Gamma(1-x+iy)} \right] \\
&+ [|\Gamma(1-x+iy)|^2] \left[\frac{\left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\Gamma(1-x-iy)] \right]}{\Gamma(1-x-iy)} \right] \\
&= [|\Gamma(1-x-iy)|^2] \left[\left[\frac{\left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\Gamma(1-x+iy)] \right]}{\Gamma(1-x+iy)} \right] \right] + \left[\left[\frac{\left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\Gamma(1-x-iy)] \right]}{\Gamma(1-x-iy)} \right] \right] \\
&= 2[|\Gamma(1-x-iy)|^2] [-Re(\Psi(1-x+iy)) - Re(\Psi(1-x-iy))] \\
&= -2[|\Gamma(1-x-iy)|^2] [Re(\Psi(1-x-iy))]
\end{aligned}$$

we get

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\left[\sin^2 \left(\frac{\pi x}{2} \right) + \sinh^2 \left(\frac{\pi y}{2} \right) \right] [|\Gamma(1-x-iy)|^2] \right] \\
&= - \left[\left[\sin^2 \left(\frac{\pi x}{2} \right) + \sinh^2 \left(\frac{\pi y}{2} \right) \right] [2|\Gamma(1-x-iy)|^2 \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(1-x-iy))] \right] \\
&+ \left[\left[\pi \sin \left(\frac{\pi x}{2} \right) \cos \left(\frac{\pi x}{2} \right) \right] [|\Gamma(1-x-iy)|^2] \right]
\end{aligned}$$

(16)

If the previously mentioned equation is equal to zero, then either both the first and the second product at the RHS should turn to zero, or one of those two products must turn negative. If “y” is not equal to 0, then there’s no chance of both those products turning zero at the same time. That leaves us with the second possibility. The second product absolutely cannot turn negative. As for the first product, $\left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\Gamma(1-x-iy)|^2] \right]$ being absolutely negative (when “x” belongs to (0, 1) and $y \geq 14$) seems to be a well-known result. Therefore, the question now changes to whether the first term is greater than the second term when $y \geq 14$.

When we expand the first term using the Digamma function, we get the negative symbol in front of the first term naturally. We can also observe that, the real part of the Digamma function is always greater than 1 when $y \geq 14$ (which is also a well-known result that can be established using the infinite sum expansion (Olver et al., 2010)). The proof is as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
\Psi(s) &= \Psi(x+iy) = -\gamma - \frac{1}{s} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{s}{n(n+s)} \\
\Psi(x+iy) &= -\gamma - \frac{1}{(x+iy)} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x+iy}{n(n+x+iy)} \\
\Psi(x+iy) &= -\gamma - \frac{(x-iy)}{(x^2+y^2)} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(x+iy)(n+x-iy)}{n[(n+x)^2+y^2]} \\
\operatorname{Re}(\Psi(x+iy)) &= -\gamma - \frac{(x)}{(x^2+y^2)} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x(n+x)+y^2}{n[(n+x)^2+y^2]} \\
\operatorname{Re}(\Psi(x+iy)) &= -\gamma - \frac{(x)}{(x^2+y^2)} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x \left(1 + \frac{x}{n} \right) + \frac{y^2}{n}}{[(n+x)^2+y^2]} \\
\operatorname{Re}(\Psi(x+iy)) &= -\gamma - \frac{(x)}{(x^2+y^2)} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\left(\frac{x}{y} \right) \left(\frac{n}{y} + \frac{x}{y} \right) + 1}{n \left[\left(\frac{n}{y} + \frac{x}{y} \right)^2 + 1 \right]}
\end{aligned}$$

The previously mentioned infinite sum is absolutely convergent within the x-interval (0, 1). The maximum value “x” can attain in this interval is “1”. Even at the maximum value, $\left(\frac{x}{y} \right)$ is still very close to zero. Regardless, let’s see what the graphs of $\operatorname{Re}(\Psi(1+iy))$ & $\operatorname{Re}(\Psi(iy))$ look like.

Plot $\text{Re}(\text{Digamma}(1+ix)); \text{Re}(\text{Digamma}(0+ix)); 0 < x < 100$

NATURAL LANGUAGE

MATH INPUT

Assuming i is the imaginary unit

Input interpretation

Plot

Plot $\text{Re}(\text{Digamma}(1+ix)); 0 < x < 100$

NATURAL LANGUAGE

MATH INPUT

Assuming i is the imaginary unit

Input interpretation

plot

$\text{Re}(\psi(1 + ix))$

$x = 0$ to 100

Plot

These two plots indicate that the two curves moved closer to one another as “ x ” moved from zero to one (most likely it moved from “0” to “1”). We thus should be able to establish that

Now comes the question of whether the real part of the Digamma function is always greater than “1” when “ y ” is greater than 14. To prove that, we first need to establish whether the Digamma function is constantly increasing with respect to “ y ”. The proof is as follows.

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial y} [\text{Re}(\Psi(x + iy))] = \frac{2xy}{(x^2 + y^2)^2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{[n((n+x)^2 + y^2)][2y] - [x(n+x) + y^2][2ny]}{n^2[(n+x)^2 + y^2]^2}$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial y} [Re(\Psi(x + iy))] = \frac{2xy}{(x^2 + y^2)^2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{[2ny][n^2 + x^2 + y^2 + 2xn - xn - x^2 - y^2]}{n^2[(n+x)^2 + y^2]^2}$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial y} [Re(\Psi(x + iy))] = \frac{2xy}{(x^2 + y^2)^2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{[2y][x+n]}{[(n+x)^2 + y^2]^2}$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial y} [Re(\Psi(x + iy))] = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{[2y][x+n]}{[(n+x)^2 + y^2]^2}$$

The previously mentioned infinite sum is always positive. We can thus see that, the real part of the Digamma function is always increasing with respect to “y”. Now comes the question of whether it is greater than “1”, when y=14. We can use a plot to confirm it.

With the partial derivative of the real part of the Digamma function with respect to “y”, we have established that “ $Re(\Psi(x + iy))$ ” is always increasing with respect to “y”. With the above plot (generated by WolframCloud), we have confirmed that “ $Re(\Psi(x + iy))$ ” is greater than “1” (thereby making it greater than $\frac{\pi}{4}$). Therefore, “ $Re(\Psi(x + iy))$ ” is greater than “1” whenever “ $y \geq 14$ ” and “x” belongs to (0, 1). “ $Re(\Psi(1 - x - iy))$ ” is just a reflection of “ $Re(\Psi(x + iy))$ ” about $x = 0.5$ (when “x” belongs to (0, 1)). Therefore, our conclusion is true for “ $Re(\Psi(1 - x - iy))$ ” as well.

Coming back to equation number 15 (or 16), let’s now discuss whether it can be equal to zero. The equation has been pasted in the following line again for better reference.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & \left[\left[\sin^2\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) + \sinh^2\left(\frac{\pi y}{2}\right) \right] [|\Gamma(1 - x - iy)|^2] \right] \\ & = - \left[\left[\sin^2\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) + \sinh^2\left(\frac{\pi y}{2}\right) \right] [2|\Gamma(1 - x - iy)|^2 Re(\Psi(1 - x - iy))] \right] \\ & + \left[\left[\pi \sin\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) \cos\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) \right] [|\Gamma(1 - x - iy)|^2] \right] \end{aligned}$$

If equation 16 is equal to zero, then

$$\left[\left[\sin^2 \left(\frac{\pi x}{2} \right) + \sinh^2 \left(\frac{\pi y}{2} \right) \right] \left[\operatorname{Re}(\Psi(1 - x - iy)) \right] \right] = \left[\left[\left(\frac{\pi}{4} \right) \sin(\pi x) \right] \right]$$

It is impossible because the LHS is always greater than one in our given constraints of “x” belonging to “(0, 0.5)” and “y” being greater than “14” (way greater than “1”. Greater than $\frac{\pi}{4}$ for sure). And the RHS is always less than $\frac{\pi}{4}$ within these given constraints.

$$\left[\sin^2 \left(\frac{\pi x}{2} \right) + \sinh^2 \left(\frac{\pi y}{2} \right) \right] \left[|\Gamma(1 - x - iy)|^2 \right] = \frac{\pi^2}{(2\pi)^{2x}}$$

This establishes that the derivative equation 16 cannot turn to zero (which implies that the previously mentioned product is monotonically decreasing in the given x-interval of (0, 0.5) & $y \geq 14$) and thus, there’s realistically no chance of the product meeting the curve $g(z) = \left[\left(\frac{(2\pi)^{2x}}{\pi^2} \right)^{-1} \right]$, when “x” belongs to (0, 0.5) (unless “x = 0.5”).

If the product didn’t have an extremum when “x” belongs to (0, 0.5), there’s a chance that it could coincide with the green curve (first graph) for multiple values of “x”. And that could only mean that, either equation 8 becomes a bump function for a particular value of “y” (which is impossible since bump functions are not analytic — it is a type of non-analytic smooth curve), or that the entire product coincides with the green curve for a particular value of “y”. That is also impossible because the Zeta function tends to “1” as “x” tends to infinity.

I had a dream about it during the early days of my investigation. In my dream, I was visualizing the modulus of the Zeta function. The function was moving along the y-axis towards infinity. Then suddenly, the waves of the function just crashed to the $z = 0$ plane for a particular value of “y” (for all values of “x”). This dream made me realize that, if the Zeta function has any complex root whose real part is not equal to 0.5, then the entire Zeta function should become a constant (that is equal to zero), for that particular value of “y”. I then woke up and realized that it is impossible since the Zeta function tends to “1” as “x” tends to infinity (since the only way the Zeta function can become a constant (that is equal to zero) inside the critical strip (for a particular value of “y”) and tend towards “1” at the same time is with a bump function that doesn’t have any cusp points for that particular value of “y”. And bump functions are not analytic (Tu, 2008). Hence the reasoning).

As the product cannot have an extremum and cannot coincide with the green curve for some or all values of “x” (for a particular value of “y”), the product is always a constant whenever a complex root point is present. This establishes my previous proof.

A similar proof can be derived using the Riemann-Xi function (Titchmarsh and Heath-Brown, 1986) as well ($|\xi(s)| = |\xi(1 - s)|$). The proof is as follows.

$$\xi(s) = \frac{s(s-1)\Gamma\left(\frac{s}{2}\right)\zeta(s)}{2\pi^{\frac{x}{2}}}$$

$$|\xi(s)|^2 = |\xi(x+iy)|^2 = \frac{(x^2 + y^2)[(x-1)^2 + y^2] \left[\left| \Gamma\left(\frac{(x+iy)}{2}\right) \right|^2 \right] \left[|\zeta(x+iy)|^2 \right]}{4\pi^x}$$

$$|\xi(1-s)|^2 = |\xi(1-x-iy)|^2$$

$$= \frac{(x^2 + y^2)[(x-1)^2 + y^2] \left[\left| \Gamma\left(\frac{(1-x-iy)}{2}\right) \right|^2 \right] [|\zeta(1-x-iy)|^2]}{4\pi^{1-x}}$$

$$\ln(|\xi(s)|^2) = \ln(x^2 + y^2) + \ln((x-1)^2 + y^2) + \ln\left(\left| \Gamma\left(\frac{(x+iy)}{2}\right) \right|^2\right) + \ln(|\zeta(x+iy)|^2) - \ln(4)$$

$$- (x)[\ln(\pi)]$$

$$\ln(|\xi(1-s)|^2) = \ln(x^2 + y^2) + \ln((x-1)^2 + y^2) + \ln\left(\left| \Gamma\left(\frac{(1-x-iy)}{2}\right) \right|^2\right)$$

$$+ \ln(|\zeta(1-x-iy)|^2) - \ln(4) - (1-x)[\ln(\pi)]$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} |\xi(s)|^2 = [|\xi(s)|^2] \left[\frac{2x}{x^2 + y^2} + \frac{2(x-1)}{(x-1)^2 + y^2} + \frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left| \Gamma\left(\frac{(x+iy)}{2}\right) \right|^2}{\left| \Gamma\left(\frac{(x+iy)}{2}\right) \right|^2} + \frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial x} |\zeta(x+iy)|^2}{|\zeta(x+iy)|^2} - \ln(\pi) \right]$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} |\xi(1-s)|^2 = [|\xi(1-x-iy)|^2] \left[\frac{2x}{x^2 + y^2} + \frac{2(x-1)}{(x-1)^2 + y^2} + \frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left| \Gamma\left(\frac{(1-x-iy)}{2}\right) \right|^2}{\left| \Gamma\left(\frac{(1-x-iy)}{2}\right) \right|^2} \right.$$

$$\left. + \frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial x} |\zeta(1-x-iy)|^2}{|\zeta(1-x-iy)|^2} + \ln(\pi) \right]$$

Since the Riemann-Xi function is a Symmetric function with respect to "x" about the plane $x = 0.5$, the derivative at both sides must be equal (i.e. $\frac{\partial}{\partial x} |\xi(s)|^2 = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} |\xi(1-s)|^2 = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} |\zeta(1-x-iy)|^2 = 0$. This is the result we are interested in). Therefore, at root points $\frac{\partial}{\partial x} |\xi(s)|^2 = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} |\xi(1-s)|^2 = 0$.

$$\left[\frac{(x^2 + y^2)[(x-1)^2 + y^2] \left[\left| \Gamma\left(\frac{(x+iy)}{2}\right) \right|^2 \right]}{4\pi^x} \right] \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} |\zeta(x+iy)|^2 \right]$$

$$= \left[\frac{(x^2 + y^2)[(x-1)^2 + y^2] \left[\left| \Gamma\left(\frac{(1-x-iy)}{2}\right) \right|^2 \right]}{4\pi^{1-x}} \right] \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} |\zeta(1-x-iy)|^2 \right] = 0$$

At root points, $\frac{\partial}{\partial x} |\zeta(x+iy)|^2 = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} |\zeta(1-x-iy)|^2 = 0$. Therefore, by using it in the previous equation, and simplifying the following equation using Bernoulli's rule (as the second derivative of $|\zeta(x+iy)|^2$ (with respect to "x"), is not equal to zero at root points), we get another root condition for the Riemann-Xi function.

$$\left[\frac{\left[\left| \Gamma\left(\frac{(x+iy)}{2}\right) \right|^2 \right]}{4\pi^x} \right] \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} |\zeta(1-x-iy)|^2 \right] = \left[\frac{\left[\left| \Gamma\left(\frac{(1-x-iy)}{2}\right) \right|^2 \right]}{4\pi^{1-x}} \right] \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} |\zeta(1-x-iy)|^2 \right]$$

$$\left[\frac{\left[\left| \Gamma \left(\frac{x+iy}{2} \right) \right|^2 \right]}{\left[\left| \Gamma \left(\frac{1-x-iy}{2} \right) \right|^2 \right]} \right] = \pi^{2x-1}$$

By using Euler's Reflection Formula ($\Gamma(m) = \frac{\pi}{[\sin(\pi m)][\Gamma(1-m)]}$) in the numerator & Legendre's Duplication Formula ($\Gamma(m) = \frac{[\Gamma(2m)][\pi^{0.5}]}{[2^{2m-1}]\Gamma(m+\frac{1}{2})}$) in the denominator, we get

$$\left[\frac{\pi^{0.5}}{[2^{x+iy}] \left[\sin \left(\frac{\pi(x+iy)}{2} \right) \right] [\Gamma(1-x-iy)]} \right]^2 = \pi^{2x-1}$$

$$\left[\frac{\pi}{[2^{2x}] \left[\sin^2 \left(\frac{\pi x}{2} \right) + \sinh^2 \left(\frac{\pi y}{2} \right) \right] [|\Gamma(1-x-iy)|^2]} \right] = \pi^{2x-1}$$

$$\left[\sin^2 \left(\frac{\pi x}{2} \right) + \sinh^2 \left(\frac{\pi y}{2} \right) \right] [|\Gamma(1-x-iy)|^2] = \frac{\pi^2}{(2\pi)^{2x}}$$

The previously derived equation is the same root condition that we have derived before. And we already know that the equation is true only when "x" is equal to "0.5".

This Hadamard product definition happened to be a wonderful definition of the Zeta function (which held the key to proving Riemann Hypothesis). And I, for one, am glad that I looked at this problem from a fresh perspective and forged my own path.

This has been an incredible journey (of one year) for me which entirely changed / transformed the way I approach Mathematics. I no longer feel like a person wandering through a dark forest without any map. I feel great as this problem proved to be an excellent learning opportunity for me, and that is more valuable to me than anything else in this world. I feel peaceful. I thank my college and my college friends who have supported me (to the fullest extent possible) during this tumultuous journey of mine as well. I dedicate this article to my late mother who has always believed in me (that I'm capable of achieving anything).

Finally, I very much would like to thank Lord Narayana (the Master of Time), who has been with me every step of the way (who has taught me everything I have ever known; the one who can see all possible versions of the future and guides me towards the one I want to be in), during this emotional journey as well.

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